

Problems and solutions "recurring" in Ecuador

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Ecuadorians face another diplomatic crisis. Last weekend, tensions with the Mexican government led to ruptures and questions that will reach the International Court of Justice. This, plus the internal commotion caused by drug trafficking, judicial corruption and embezzlement, make Ecuador a country with a weak democracy.

The headlines in the media report crimes on a daily basis. In the last two months, the networks between criminals, judges, police, lawyers, and politicians who have agreed to divide up territories and "lines of business" have become evident.

In the face of these human and social crises, many cannot find work, because there are also huge running costs and little investment in public administration. Thus, emigration continues by illegal means. Hundreds are caught in nets that leave them to fend for themselves in jungles and at borders. Those who remain in their homelands have less security, less income and more uncertainty.

Where does the solution start? The easy answer is to change the government, to wait for a "messiah" or a divine "panacea" to rescue the "just and sinners", that is, to think that others, and not each person, have a chance to improve the country. But, as the popular adage says, "for great evils, great remedies" implies getting involved, participating, cooperating.

Many see what is happening in Ecuador as an inevitability, however, thinking like these only distances us from solutions. In the construction of ways to achieve harmony and a longed-for peace, the media are committed to incorporating a positive, encouraging narrative that shows the truth and also encourages citizen intervention.